

Accountability Regimes and International Climate Change Financing: The Green Climate Fund

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Abstract

This paper uses a mixed method approach to analyze the accountability regime of the largest global climate change financing institution, the Green Climate Fund. Through the content analysis of institutional documents and a series of key informant interviews of the various actors across the accountability regime (i.e., from board members to recipient organizations and civil society stakeholders), we gain a better understanding of the roles of such actors as account holders and accountees. This also allows us to describe in rich detail the accountability elements (following Mashaw, 2006) of the regime, namely who is accountable to whom, about what, through which process, according to what standards and facing what penalties. The paper also offers recommendations to improve the accountability regime of the Green Climate Fund and for international climate financing more broadly.

Keywords: Accountability, climate change financing, Green Climate Fund, adaptation, mitigation.

Introduction

The Green Climate Fund (GCF), established by the Conference of the Parties (COP) of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) at its sixteenth session, held in Cancun in 2010 (UNFCCC, 2011) is a new international flagship institution that is intended to play a key role in mobilizing Climate Finance of \$100 billion a year by 2020. The GCF offices, based in Incheon City, Republic of Korea, opened in December 2013 and the institution only recently began funding projects, with a first round of projects approved in December of 2015¹. As such, it is indeed a multilateral organization that is at a nascent stage.

The sheer size of of financing that is hoped to be mobilized behooves the institution to set up an accountability regime that is worthy of the financing that it will allocate. Failing that, the GCF will face pressure from donor countries, who have made significant contributions to the GCF, recipient countries in the developing world, who expect the GCF to provide the much-needed funds for them to mitigate and adapt to climate change, as well as civil society organizations.

This paper will address the following question: What does the accountability regime of the largest global climate change financing institution, the Green Climate Fund, look like - which actors are seeking to hold it to account, how, according to what standards?

Accountability, in its simplest definition, is a relationship between at least two individuals - one giving account to the other. Or as As Romzek & Dubnick (1987) describe it: “*answerability for one’s actions or behaviour*” (p.228). In a broader context of governance, according to Mashaw (2006), this begs questions such as: who is accountable? To whom? For what? What is the process whereby account can be given?

¹ <http://www.greenclimate.fund>

Against what is the account to be judged? What are the impacts or penalties² associated with poor performance?

This paper provides an attempt to make a comprehensive description and analysis of the GCF's accountability regime. The paper is organized as follows: the next section describes materials and methods. This is followed by a presentation of results from the content analysis, as well as the key informant interviews. The paper then offers concluding comments and considerations for international climate financing.

Materials and Methods

This paper uses mixed methods to analyze the formal and informal accountability elements of the institution, as well as the key actors – account holders and those giving account. In order to provide a description of the elements of the accountability regime for the GCF, content analysis of GCF institutional documents, as well as key informant interviews are used. The review of institutional documents (via content analysis, using Atlas.ti) enables to identify formal accountability elements, whereas interviews enable to see how those formal relationships are enacted (i.e., managerial, professional and personal accountability (as described by Sinclair, 1995)), and also identify informal accountability pressures (i.e., informal internal sources and by formal and informal external sources (as described by Romzek and Dubnick, 1987)).

Documents for review

The two main document types reviewed were “institutional documents” and “project proposals”. Institutional documents were limited to the latest versions of documents approved by the Green Climate Fund Board and the Conference of the Parties of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change and available online. This did not include Board meeting minutes. Project proposals were also limited to the latest versions of documents approved by the Green Climate Fund Board and available on the GCF website. All documents were collected during the period of March and June 2016. A total of 27 documents were subjected to content analysis.

Key informant interviews

The first step for the key informant interviews was to determine the target population and possible key informants, that is, the main actors in the accountability regime of the GCF, namely:

- GCF Board members (from donor and developing countries)
- National Designated Authorities
- Accredited Entities
- Non-governmental and civil society organizations

In total, 60 potential informants were contacted to participate in the study and 14 interviews were conducted. The key informant interviews were semi-structured and mostly used “mini tour” questions, that is, questions that require respondents to provide details on particular or more specific issues or experiences (Spradley 1979). Closed questions were also used to probe and obtain additional details from respondents, as suggested by Holstein and Gubrium (1995).

² Bovens (2007) outlines several types of penalties, both formal and informal: “*finer, disciplinary measures, civil remedies or even penal sanctions, but they can also be based on unwritten rules, as in the case of the political accountability of a minister to parliament, where the consequence can comprise calling for the minister’s resignation.*” (p.452).

Once interviews were completed, the audio recordings were sent to a professional transcript writer. The transcripts were then verified and completed by the interviewer, in order to fill in any inaudible sections. The final transcripts were then imported into Atlas.ti and the coding process used was the same as described in the “Document coding” section above.

Results from the Document Review

Account Holders

In the documents reviewed, the most significant account holder is by far the GCF Board, with 169 quotations coded related to the GCF Board’s role as an account holder. The Accreditation Master Agreement contained the most quotations related to the GCF Board as account holder (42 quotations). The Accredited Entities (as financing recipients) are account holders in 55 quotations, mainly found in the eight individual project proposals for the first round of funding. They are account holders vis-à-vis implementing partners and sub-grantees (i.e., an accountability ‘cascade’ or chain), as per the Accreditation Master Agreement they are required to sign for their accountability to the GCF Board. It is important to note that in 22 quotations, Accredited Entities also act as the account holder in an accountability cascade with implementing partners and sub-grantees.

The GCF Secretariat Management (including the Executive Director’s roles and responsibilities) is another important account holder, with 35 quotations. This is followed closely by the Conference of the Parties at 27. Interestingly, 37 quotations were related to NGO, CSO, PSO and other stakeholders as account holders, whereas blended donors, who are the true financiers of the GCF, were only mentioned as account holders 19 times in the documents reviewed.

Accountees

Accredited Entities are by far the most mentioned as accountees, with 149 quotes across several key documents, including the the Accreditation Master Agreements (45 quotations), the eight individual project proposals for the first round of funding (39 quotations) the Monitoring and Accountability Framework for Accredited Entities (33 quotations), the Fiduciary Principles and Standards of the Fund (15 quotations) and the Governing Instrument of the GCF (11 quotations).

The GCF Board and the GCF Secretariat have 36 and 33 quotations each related to their role as accountee. Some of the projects approved in the first round of funding identify many accountability elements between the AE and the GCF, but also between the AE and its implementing partners, thus presenting a rather long accountability chain.

Accountable About What?

The most quotations were found to be related to accountability about management (100 quotations), reporting (95 quotations), evaluation (85 quotations), monitoring (82 quotations) and performance (62 quotations).

Penalties

There were 33 quotations found related to penalties in the GCF accountability regime. 20 of these quotations were in the Accreditation Master Document. Indeed, the co-occurrence of “penalties” and “Accredited Entities” is 72% (i.e., the two codes co-occur 72% of the time).

Many of the penalties, including the ‘downgrading’ of the status of Accredited Entities are set out in the Monitoring and Accountability Framework of the GCF.

Results from Key Informant Interviews

Donor country GCF Board members

Through the course of the two donor country board member interviews, the GCF board's role as accountee was mentioned more often than its role as account holder (30 quotations Vs 18 quotations). Accountability about management (17 quotations), performance (18 quotations) and reporting (2 quotations) was mentioned by the two board members interviewed.

Board members differentiated between formal and informal measures in the accountability regime, with 27 quotations being related to formal accountability measures, whereas 21 being related to informal measures. Another board spoke to the role of transparency in the accountability regime and argued that making board meetings available for viewing via webcast can enable informal accountability from CSOs.

Developing country GCF Board members

Accountability for management (55 quotations), monitoring (3 quotations), reporting (11 quotations) and performance (26 quotations) are mentioned by the three developing country board members. The developing country board member(s) put a significant amount of emphasis on the need to hold key actors (GCF board, NDAs) accountable for engagement and for the GCF to be accountable for proper management (three times as many quotations on this subject compared to their donor country board member counterparts).

Developing country board member mentioned the role of the COP as account holder more frequently than donor country board members (26 quotations Vs 3). Developing country board members also saw the GCF board as being accountable to recipient countries and the constituent countries developing country board members represent. Donors to the GCF are also seen as important account holders (15 quotations), although recipient countries are mentioned as account holders in 17 quotations. 78 quotations pertain to the GCF as accountee Vs 37 quotations mentioning the GCF as account holder. 21 quotations are related to AEs as accountees and 12 are related to NDAs as accountees.

National Designated Authorities/Focal points

NDAs see themselves mainly accountable to their home country and both NDAs interviewed mentioned being accountable for engagement (6 and 5 quotations each). This is not surprising, as the main role of NDAs is to engage various actors within their respective countries to ensure that solid country-led proposals are submitted to the GCF. Six quotations were related to being accountable for sharing information with key stakeholders, which is also part of their role as NDA according to the documentation reviewed.

Accredited entities

Accredited entities see the GCF board as their main account holder (37 quotations), although they mention their own role as account holder vis-à-vis other implementing agents that they would work with in the context of project implementation (16 quotations related to AE as account holder). This validates what was found in the document review. 50 quotations were related to AE as accountee (3 times as many as AE as account holder). This again validates findings from the document review, which show that AEs are the most often mentioned accountee (149 quotations in all documents reviewed).

Accountability about management is most often mentioned by AEs (32 quotations), followed by reporting (18 quotations) and performance (17 quotations). 15 quotations were related to recipient countries as accountees. This is because the three key informants interviewed were in AEs who work closely with recipient country government institutions as important project implementing partners. They also mentioned the importance of country ownership in the preparation of project proposals for submission to the GCF, which is in-line with the documentation reviewed.

CSOs

The three respondents from civil society organizations that participated in this study provided responses that were very similar amongst the three. The vast majority of their commentary was related to CSOs as being account holders (60 quotations). This is followed by the GCF Board as account holder (14 quotations) and interestingly, citizens as account holders (11 quotations). As for who they perceive as being key accountees, they mention the GCF Board twice as often as grant recipients (49 quotations Vs 23 quotations).

When asked who CSOs were ultimately accountable to, all 3 respondents stated that they were accountable to each other, their network or to the constituency they represent. However, without clarity and formality around the process whereby they can give account and face penalties or reprimands for their actions, if warranted, this can be an important gap in the accountability regime.

During the interviews, CSO respondents also voiced their concern about the potential barrier that the GCF accreditation process could pose, especially for developing country institutions that are seeking accreditation. They also mentioned the lack of meaningful CSO representation in the management of the GCF, with only two CSO observers, which cannot represent the broad-ranging positions of environmental NGOs, citizens' groups and indigenous peoples, for instance.

Another key issue outlined by CSO respondents is the lack of capacity in developing countries, which can lead to, for example, NDAs that are not knowledgeable about their own country's climate change priorities, let alone have the experience required to engage the right actors to ensure solid project proposals are developed and presented to the GCF Board.

Conclusions

Key documents have been analyzed and the main actors in the accountability regime have been interviewed. The majority of the accountability mechanisms are found in three documents, mainly the funding proposals submitted to the GCF board, the GCF governing instrument and the Accreditation Master Agreement. Ex ante accountability mechanisms play a significant role in the regime, with the accreditation process of potential recipients being an important element. Ex post mechanisms, on the other hand, do not play as significant a role, with penalties and rewards being seldom mentioned in the documents reviewed and in the interviews, compared to ex ante mechanisms. How or whether the penalties are enforced, and whether they provide sufficient incentives for the various actors to perform as expected, will only be determined once projects start being implemented.

The main account holder in the regime is the GCF board, whereas the main accountees are the accredited entities. As for what accountees are accountable for, the most oft-quoted responsibilities in the documents reviewed were management, reporting, monitoring and performance. This was echoed in the interviews with most actors, especially developing country board members.

The GCF's accountability regime is heavily focused on accredited entities and would benefit from formalizing accountability elements pertaining to other actors within the regime. The role of COP should be strengthened to close the current accountability gap, as the GCF could be perceived as not being truly accountable to anyone.

References

- Bovens, M. (2007). Analysing and Assessing Accountability : A Conceptual Framework. *European Law Journal*, 13(4), 447–468. Retrieved from http://www.graduateschool.edu.pl/sns/pliki/Wierzba/M_Bovens_Analysing.pdf
- Holstein, J. A., & Gubrium, J. F. (1995). *The Active Interview*. SAGE Publications. Retrieved from <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=LgR3TjzCxf8C&pgis=1>
- Mashaw, J. L. (2006). Accountability and Institutional Design: Some Thoughts on the Grammar of Governance. In M. Dowdle (Ed.), *Public Accountability: Designs, Dilemmas and Experiences* (pp. 115–156). Cambridge University Press. Retrieved from <http://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=924879>
- Romzek, B. S., & Dubnick, M. J. (1987). Accountability in the Public Sector: Lessons from the Challenger Tragedy. *Public Administration Review*, 47(3), 227–238. <http://doi.org/10.2307/975901>
- Spradley, J. P. (1979). *The Ethnographic Interview*. Holt, Rinehart and Winston. Retrieved from https://books.google.com/books?id=XP5_AAAAMAAJ&pgis=1
- UNFCCC. (2011). *Report of the Conference of the Parties on its sixteenth session, held in Cancun from 29 November to 10 December 2010. Decision 1/CP.16*. Retrieved from <http://unfccc.int/resource/docs/2010/cop16/eng/07a01.pdf>